

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to Dr. V. S. Misra, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Lucknow for facilities and to the Director, C. D. R. I., Lucknow for spectral and elemental analysis.

References

1. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1975, 64, 881.
2. T. S. OSDANE, "Medicinal Chemistry", 3rd Edn., (Ed.) A. BERGER, Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970, 662.
3. R. CAVIER, R. ROVER, R. RIPS and L. BENE, *Chim. Ther.*, 1969, 4, 21.
4. E. HAMBSCH, *German patent*, 1019459, 1975; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 196738.
5. KUPINIC, MIRJANO, MEDIC-SARIC, MARICA, MAVERIN, MURITA, MAYSINGER, *Dusica. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1979, 68, 459; *Chem. Abs.*, 1980, 91, 758.
6. R. S. VARMA and I. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1978, 67, 315.
7. J. WYETH and Brothers Ltd., *Brit. Pat.*, 1240648, 1971; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 118942.
8. M. B. MAHISHI, B. H. IYER and M. SIRSI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 42, 67.
9. C. S. MARREL and O. S. HIERS, "Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. I, 1941, 327.
10. W. C. SUMPTER and W. F. JONES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1802.
11. JOHN HARLEY-MENSON and R. F. J. INGLEBY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 8639.
12. H. L. YALE, K. LOSER, J. MARTINS, M. HOLSING, F. M. PERRY and J. BERNSTEIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1933.
13. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1952, 8, 249.
14. O. ISLER, H. GILMAN, O. STRAUB, B. FAST, E. BARNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 38, 1088.

Synthesis of Substituted 6-Pyrazolo and 6-Isoxazolo-Benzoxazoles and Their Physiological Activity

M. SADASIVA SHANKAR, B. RAJESHWARA RAO,
G. V. P. CHANDRA MOULI and Y. D. REDDY
Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College,
Warangal-506 004

Manuscript received 24 December 1981, accepted 7 June 1982

A wide range of physiological properties are found to be associated with benzoxazoles, isoxazoles and pyrazoles. Heterocycles, substituted with hydroxyphenyl moiety, have been used as analgesic¹, antitissuive² and anticonvulsant³ agents. A number of hydroxyaryl pyrazoles were found to possess marked antifungal activity⁴. The present investigation is aimed at a study of antifungal activity of some substituted isoxazolobenzoxazoles and pyrazolobenzoxazoles and a series of the above new compounds are synthesised and screened for antifungal and antibacterial activities.

Chromones in their reactions with hydrazine or phenylhydrazine behave like α,β -unsaturated ketones

and undergo Michael addition. The nucleophile attacks at C-2 with concomitant opening of the pyrone ring. The intermediates thus formed undergo cyclisation to give 3(5)-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-pyrazole system^{5,6}.

Chart 1. R=alkyl or aryl; R'=H or ph

In the present investigation, the behaviour of some substituted chromonooxazoles with hydroxylamine, hydrazine and phenylhydrazine is studied. Substituted chromonooxazoles can be prepared starting from *o*-hydroxyaminochromones either by treating with various aldehydes in nitrobenzene⁷ or treatment with carboxylic acids in presence of polyphosphoric acid⁸.

Chromonooxazoles (I), upon treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine, underwent the cleavage of the chromone ring followed by the formation of isoxazole unit, resulting in the formation of II. The same chromonooxazole (I), when treated with hydrazinehydrate or phenylhydrazine in alcohol medium yielded III (Chart 2). These results are in accordance with Ghosh *et al.*⁹.

Chart 2

All the products gave green colouration with neutral ferric chloride, pink colour with conc. sulphuric acid and dark violet colour with titanium(III) chloride. The uv maxima are recorded at 250 ± 10 nm due to benzoxazole chromophore and at 280 ± 10 nm due to extended conjugation. The ir bands at 1570, 1350, 1050 cm^{-1} are characteristic of oxazole ring system. A broad absorption at 3200 cm^{-1} is for chelated hydroxyl group. Further, absorption at 1640 cm^{-1} is indicative of >C=N . The pmr results have been included in Table 1.

Physiological activity :

All the above compounds have been tested for antibacterial activity using *Staphylococcus lutea*,

NOTES

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Compound	Assignment					Substituent at 2	Substituent at N
		3'-OH ₂	4'H	4H, 5H	Chelated 7-OH			
1.	2- <i>o</i> -Toluyyl-6-(5'-methylisoxazole-3'-yl)-7-hydroxybenzoxazole	2.8(s) (5'-Me)	6.6(s)	8.1(m)	10.4 to 10.6 (broad)	2.8(s) Me, 7.2 to 7.6 (m) ar. protons	—	
2.	2-Phenyl-6-(3'-methylpyrazole-5'-yl)-7-hydroxybenzoxazole	2.4(s)	6.6(s)	8.2(m)	10.4 to 10.6 (broad)	7.4 to 7.7(m) ar. protons	2.5 (broad) (N-H)	
3.	2- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-6'-(1'-phenyl-8'-methylpyrazole-5'-yl)-7-hydroxybenzoxazole	2.4(s)	6.3(s)	8.2(m)	10.4 to 10.6 (broad)	2.7(s) Me, 7.2 to 7.5(m) ar. protons (4H)	7.2 to 7.5(m) aromatic (5H)	

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Compound	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	
2-(R)-6-(5'-Methylisoxazole-3'-yl)-7-hydroxybenzoxazole							
R							
1.	Phenyl	222	76	72.6 (72.8)*	4.3 (4.2)	10.1 (10.0)	
2.	(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl)	224	74	64.7 (64.8)	3.5 (3.4)	8.8 (8.9)	
3.	(2-Naphthyl)	236	72	73.7 (73.6)	4.1 (4.0)	8.2 (8.1)	
4.	(3-Pyridyl)	240	68	69.1 (69.3)	3.8 (3.9)	15.3 (15.1)	
5.	<i>o</i> -Toluyyl	192	77	78.3 (78.4)	4.6 (4.7)	9.4 (9.5)	
6.	<i>p</i> -Toluyyl	200	78	73.2 (73.4)	4.5 (4.7)	9.6 (9.5)	
2-(R)-6-(1'-R'-3'-Methylpyrazole-5'-yl)-7-hydroxybenzoxazole							
	R	R'					
1.	Phenyl	Phenyl	207	82	75.0 (75.2)	4.9 (4.8)	11.5 (11.4)
2.	Phenyl	H	300	80	68.9 (68.8)	4.8 (4.7)	15.2 (15.0)
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	282	78	68.6 (68.7)	4.0 (3.9)	10.5 (10.4)
4.	2-Naphthyl	Phenyl	272	81	77.5 (77.6)	4.4 (4.5)	10.2 (10.0)
5.	6-Methyl-3-coumarinyl	Phenyl	260	79	72.4 (72.3)	3.9 (4.0)	9.4 (9.3)

* Figures in parentheses are calculated values.

S. aureus, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus magetenium* as representative species, employing glass humid chamber technique. None of the compounds are found to be antibacterial. The antifungal activity has been assessed by employing *Drechslera rostrata* (Drechs) and *Alternaria alternata* (Keissler) as the test organisms. All the compounds tested could inhibit the spore germination at 30 µg/ml up to the maximum level. Hence it is concluded that all the compounds possess high antifungal activity but not antibacterial.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra are recorded on Perkin-Elmer 297 instrument in KBr pellets. NMR is recorded on a Varian

A-60 MHz instrument. Micro analysis is done on Hewlett-Packard 185-B Model. The data are given in Table 2.

All the chromonooxazoles were prepared by procedures reported earlier^{7,8}

2-Substituted-6-(5'-methylisoxazole-3-yl)-7-hydroxybenzoxazoles: The parent chromonooxazole and hydroxylamine hydrochloride were taken in equimolar ratio and dissolved in pyridine, refluxed for 4 hr and excess pyridine removed by distillation. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and neutralised with dilute acetic acid with constant stirring. The resulting solid product was washed thoroughly with cold water and dried. All the compounds were recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether. Yields were above 80%.

2-Substituted-6-[(1'-substituted-3'-methylpyrazol-5'-yl)]-7-hydroxybenzoxazoles: All the N-phenyl pyrazolyl and pyrazolyl substituted benzoxazoles were prepared by taking equimolar proportions of chromonooxazole and phenylhydrazine or hydrazine hydrate in alcohol and refluxing and working out in the above manner.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Principal, Regional Engineering College, Warangal for facilities and Prof. S. R. Ramadas, Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras for valuable suggestions. One of the authors (M.S.S.) is thankful to the Principal, C. K. M. College, Warangal for encouragement. The authors are also grateful to Dr. M. A. Singaracharya, Lecturer, C. K. M. College, for kind help in testing antifungal and antibacterial activities.

References

1. J. LEE, H. ZIERING, S. D. HEINEMANN and L. BERGER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, 12, 885.
2. O. J. BRAENDEN, N. B. EDDY and B. HARACH, *Bull. World. Health Org.*, 1955, 13, 935.
3. A. H. BACKET and A. F. COSY, *Bull. Narcot.*, 1957, 9, 37.
4. T. O. SHARMA, M. M. BOKADIA and N. J. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, 19B, 228.
5. W. BAKER, J. B. HORBORNE and W. D. OGLIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1305.
6. A. SCHOENBERG and M. M. SIDKY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5128.
7. Y. D. REDDY and V. V. SOMAYAJULU, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1971, 74, 265.
8. Y. D. REDDY and V. V. SOMAYAJULU, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1975, 82, 230.
9. C. K. GHOSH and K. K. MUKHOPADHYAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 50, 52.

A Field Test for The Detection and Semiquantitative Determination of Sulphurdioxide in Air and Water

(Miss) ABHA CHAUBE and V. K. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010

Manuscript received 16 October 1981, revised 11 March 1982, accepted 1 May 1982

SULPHURDIOXIDE is a major pollutant originating from industrial and domestic emissions. It is also a major component of automobile exhaust and its applications as a preservative or fungicide are major sources of sulphurdioxide pollution. The "Threshold Limit Value" adopted by American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (1969) is 5 ppm¹. In view of its hazardous effects on health, vegetation and property², a fast and reliable method for detection of traces of sulphurdioxide would be of immense value.

In search of better organic bases to increase the intensity of brick red colouration in the Bodeker

reaction³, it was found that malonyldihydrazide (MDH) along with zinc acetate and sodium nitroprusside gives a very intense brick red precipitate in solution. The reaction is used for spot test to detect as low as 0.2 ppm sulphurdioxide in air or water.

Experimental

Preparation of malonyldihydrazide: Malonyldihydrazide was prepared by adding hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mole in alcohol) to an alcoholic solution of diethyl malonate (0.05 mole in alcohol) in 2:1 mole ratio. The white solid obtained was crystallised from water, m.p. 150°.

Reagents: (1) 1 M zinc acetate solution in 5% v/v glycerol, (2) 2% w/v solution of sodium nitroprusside in distilled water and (3) 2% w/v solution of malonyldihydrazide in distilled water were used.

Sulphurdioxide for air analysis was prepared from freshly prepared sodium sulphite solution in water with a small amount of HCl.

All reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Procedure

Spot test for the detection of sulphurdioxide as sulphite ions in water: 1 ml of each of the above mentioned reagents 1, 2 and 3 were taken in a 10 ml beaker serially. A cream coloured colloidal solution was formed. The solution was stable for a week. One drop of this solution was taken on a spot plate. One drop of sulphurdioxide solution (5 µg/ml) was added to this spot. A brick red precipitate formed immediately which indicated the presence of sulphurdioxide. The precipitate was stable for more than 24 hr.

Detection in air: Test papers were prepared and examined for the detection of traces of sulphurdioxide in air by the earlier reported method⁴ using 2% w/v solution of malonyldihydrazide along with 1 M zinc acetate solution and 2% sodium nitroprusside solution. The colour produced in the test paper was compared with that obtained from passing 1 litre of air containing 0.1 to 2 ppm of sulphurdioxide. A semiquantitative determination was possible.

Results and Discussion

The present method is more sensitive than the earlier reported methods. Brick red precipitate is not soluble in organic solvents like chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, butanol, methanol, ethanol, methyl acetate, etc. Precipitate is either decomposed or remains undissolved in these solvents.

Carbonate, chloride, sulphate, ammonia, nitrate, nitrite, phosphate did not interfere in this reaction. Sulphide ion was found to give similar colour reaction. However, the interference from sulphide ion can be eliminated by passing the air sample through mercuric chloride solution.